

**CHEMICAL CONTAMINATION AND CHANGES IN THE ECOLOGICAL
CONDITION OF SOILS AROUND THE ANGREN THERMAL POWER STATION IN
THE TASHKENT REGION.**

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Annotation. This article talks about the impact of toxic fumes and wastes produced by industrial enterprises on the physico-biochemical condition of the soil, which is considered one of the urgent issues of today, in order to provide the population with ecologically clean and nutritious food products.

Keywords: environment, slag, soil, pollution, ecology, waste, factors, fertility, ecosystem.

Significance and research of the topic: Providing clean food products to today's population is considered one of the vital issues. The efficient utilization of industrially produced polluted soils is one of the scientific research's primary objectives; maintaining their ecological conditions, and changing the sustainable development of the ecosystem. Mainly, environmental pollution is divided into two categories. *The first* is naturally occurring chemicals that pollute the environment as a result of natural disasters such as volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, meteorites, storms, hurricanes, fires, and droughts; *the second* is divided into chemicals (manufacturing industry, service industry) which are produced by the chemical industry. The effects of the thermal power plant on the extensive local vegetation were examined during the scientific investigation. Nowadays, the increase in the population of our country requires rational use of their ecosystem. Because we all need to know, that only soil is the layer that produces food products that are necessary for humans. The operation of the soil's thermal power station has an impact on the soil's fertility and, in some cases, renders it unusable. In this regard, many foreign researchers have conducted scientific research, including some scientists who have studied the pollution of the water ecosystem as a result of the operation of the power plant in Moldavia. According to the results of the conducted research, it was found that metals are accumulated in the tissues of aquatic organisms. In addition, because of the operation of the thermal power plant, it was determined that chemical elements such as Mo, V, Ni, Pb, Cu, and Zn in the water exceeded the permissible limit[1]. In addition, it has been studied by researchers that coal-fired thermal power plants in Russia are a constant source of environmental pollution, which has an increased negative impact on the health of the population and the environment. There is soil pollution with ash and slag as a result of coal combustion, atmospheric air pollution with nitrogen oxide, and technogenic pollution of water bodies and soils due to the spread of chemicals[2]. The waste which is accumulated as a result of industrial activities leads to changes in the chemical composition of the soil and the reduction of natural landscapes[3]. Barapukuria Coal-Fired Thermal Power Plant in Bangladesh was built in 2006 and is the first coal-fired power plant in Bangladesh. This plant consumed 0.72 million tons of coal per year, and as a

result, 0.08 million tons of coal ash were formed. In addition, various heavy metals such as Sd, Zn, AS, Pb from industrial enterprises have shown their negative effects on the environment, including ecosystems. As a result of the waste, metals have caused contamination of water sources, soil, and food crops around industrial areas[4]. Currently, the waste of any industrial enterprise operating around the world leads to manufactured pollution of the soil and deterioration of its composition, therefore, systematic implementation of waste processing causes less damage to the environment[5].

The aim and objectives of the research: The research aims to determine the criteria for chemical contamination of dark gray soils irrigated around the thermal power plant, which is located in the city of Angren, Tashkent region.

The objectives of the research are as follows:

- To determine the amount of chemical pollution of dark gray soils irrigated around the thermal power station;
- To analyze the level of pollution over the years.

Research methods: The studies were carried out on irrigated gray-meadow soils around the Joint-Stock Company "Uzbek Metallurgical Plant" in the city of Bekabad, Tashkent region. Heavy metals and other compounds in soil were tested under laboratory conditions following MP 003:2015.

Research results: Thermal power plants operating in some countries by foreign scientists to soils and plants, also we can see from the literature analysis that it affected living organisms and caused changes in their ecological characteristics. Therefore, to conduct scientific research, it is necessary to study the changes in environmental conditions as a result of the operation of the Angren thermal power station located in the Tashkent region. Scientific studies were conducted to study the ecological conditions of soils, plants, and living organisms scattered in the area. During the research, it was found that the Angren Thermal Power Station mainly harmed the ecological conditions of the soil by causing a decrease in its productivity. Figure 1 shows the amounts of chemical compounds, including heavy metals, accumulated in the soil because of the operation of the Angren Thermal Power Station.

Fig.1

The impact of the activities of the Angren Thermal Power Station on the soil was studied during the years 2020, 2021, and 2022. As you can see in the figure above, the amount of chemical elements in the soil has been increasing over the years. Among them, it was found that As-4.1 times and Ni-2.7 times exceeded the allowable limit.

Conclusion. According to the indicators defined above, one of the important issues is the preservation of the ecological state of technogenically polluted soils scattered across the territory of the Angren Thermal Power Plant, and their purification through reclamation, depending on the degree of pollution. As a result, the soil's ecological state is restored, irrigated lands are used more effectively, and food that is good for the environment is grown.

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